

THE DEGREE OF PRACTICING DISTRIBUTED LEADERSHIP BY PRINCIPALS OF ARAB SCHOOLS IN THE NORTHERN DISTRICT WITHIN THE GREEN LINE FROM TEACHER'S POINT OF VIEW

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Abstract

The aim of this study was to identify the degree of practicing distributed leadership by principals of Arab Schools in the northern district within the green line from teachers point of view, and to know the impact of variables (sex, educational qualification, number of years of experience) at that degree, a descriptive survey approach was used, a questionnaire was also used as a tool to collect the necessary data to achieve the objectives of the study, the study sample consisted of (385) teachers, selected by a simple random method, the results of the study showed that the degree of practicing distributed leadership by principals of Arab Schools in the northern district within the green line from teacher's point of view was high, the results, further, indicated that there were no significant statistical differences at ($\alpha=0.05$) in sample's estimates of the degree of practicing distributed leadership by principals due to (sex, educational qualification, number of years of experience) variables.

Keywords: Distributed Leadership, Arab School Principals, Teachers, the Northern District, The Green Line.

Introduction

In the field of educational work, it is observed that contemporary daily life is witnessing a noticeable acceleration due to rapid and continuous developments and changes in the fields of human knowledge, digital and technological knowledge, and significant transformations in the field of information and communication technology. As a result, it has become difficult for individuals and societies to avoid the demands and conditions of life. Therefore, it is essential to keep pace with these developments and the challenges arising from them, which justifies the importance of having an education system that renews, evolves, and prepares to face future horizons. To achieve this goal, school administration and leadership must possess strength characterized by cooperation and flexibility, and be capable of developing everyone's abilities toward achieving success and leadership in the fields of administration and education.

Distributed leadership is a modern approach aimed at achieving the desired goals of the school by investing the available human and material resources. Recently, the distributed leadership style has increasingly appeared in the Arab region. Its emergence is a result of the transformations witnessed in the education sector, where more tasks and responsibilities have been added to school staff. Consequently, there is an urgent need to use a new leadership model based on the principle of mutual trust, inquiry, support, and cooperation among all school staff, enabling them to perform their assigned tasks and duties efficiently and effectively (Al-Masara, 2019).

The concept of distributed leadership is considered one of the modern concepts, and it began to circulate in the 1950s, specifically in 1950 by Gibb. Thus, this concept is one of the oldest recommended leadership concepts for achieving institutional goals by activating the role of employees (Al-Zaki and Hammad, 2011). Distributed leadership is defined as "an administrative approach based on participation and democracy in managing school affairs, encouraging the administrative empowerment of teachers by the school principal distributing leadership tasks among teachers, making them responsible for making and implementing decisions, and carrying out tasks to achieve the school's goals in the least time and effort possible" (Mohammed, 2020, p. 180).

In the past, the school principal was the sole responsible for administration, and had to be a successful teacher to reach this position. Years of service were the primary criterion for promotion. However, with the development of the education sector, the roles, tasks, and responsibilities placed on school staff have increased, leading to the emergence of a new style of educational leadership, namely distributed leadership. This style encourages the activation of staff roles and their participation in institutional decision-making and achieving common goals (Dartel, 2013). Currently, schools differ from the past in the type of administration and leadership, making it difficult to predict their structural development. This requires adopting a new form of leadership in schools, where the principal plays a pivotal role. For a school principal to apply distributed leadership, they must be familiar with political competencies, which are an important factor in developing leadership capabilities in all aspects of the school. Among the essential roles that a school principal should perform is the role of a political expert, where the principal has political competence in dealing with the local community as a strong educational leader (Terrell, 2010).

A distributed school leader must be an educational facilitator by emphasizing that teachers' influence and inspiration on students is the key element to their success, and thus the school's success in achieving its goals. This requires the school principal to adopt an educational vision aimed at enhancing cooperation among school community members, guiding teachers to adopt modern teaching methods, and encouraging their professional development. This should be done in an atmosphere of trust and positive, fruitful interaction among the educational and administrative team members in the school (Onukwugha, 2013).

Sa'ima (2017) indicated that distributed leadership aims to enhance cooperation, empower administrative and educational teams to make joint decisions, and identify priorities and strategies that contribute to improving school and educational performance comprehensively. This approach relies on understanding the diverse capabilities and skills of school staff and optimally investing them to achieve the school's shared vision and goals.

Distributed leadership generally focuses on the idea of everyone's participation in leadership within the institution. It can be envisioned as a belief in the idea of a leadership team and the belief that authority or leadership should not be concentrated in the hands of one person but should be available to everyone. Its idea is based on the need for educational institutions to have more leaders due to the increasing complexity of their administration and leadership, which calls for abandoning traditional leadership styles that rely on the idea of a single leader and adopting more democratic leadership styles (Harris et al., 2022).

A review of educational literature and previous studies on distributed school leadership reveals a set of distinctive dimensions of distributed leadership. These dimensions are considered fundamental factors that contribute to the development and improvement of educational performance and the enhancement of the learning environment in the school. Scribner et al. (2007) pointed out that the **teacher dimension** is one of the most important dimensions of distributed

leadership, focusing on developing teachers' skills and abilities. The teacher represents the backbone of the learning process, and therefore it is necessary to provide the necessary support and guidance to improve their performance and increase their effectiveness in teaching. This requires providing training opportunities, workshops, and technical assistance to ensure the development of their teaching skills and motivate them to innovate and adopt modern and effective teaching methods. Brown et al. (2000) identified three dimensions of distributed leadership: **the school's vision and mission dimension**: The school's vision and mission are vital factors in directing efforts toward achieving educational goals. The vision should be clear and specific, reflecting the school's goals and aspirations, and all members of the educational team should feel connected to the school's vision and participate in achieving it. **The results dimension**: Achieving tangible results is a strong indicator of the effectiveness of distributed leadership. Therefore, performance and results should be analyzed and evaluated periodically to ensure continuous improvement. This can be achieved by utilizing data and information to make sound decisions and improve the educational process. **The school leadership dimension**: In addition to the role of teachers, school leadership plays a pivotal role in directing efforts toward achieving goals. Therefore, leaders should have the ability to motivate and guide the educational team toward achieving excellence and improving performance. Terrell (2010) mentioned four dimensions of distributed leadership: the school's vision, mission, and goals, followed by the school's culture, then shared responsibility, and finally leadership practices.

The researcher concludes that these dimensions' work as an integrated set to achieve success and development in the educational environment by focusing on developing teachers, guiding the school's vision and mission, achieving tangible results, and effectively leading the school. This achieves continuous improvement and contributes to achieving the best learning outcomes. In this study, the researcher adopted the following dimensions: the school's vision and mission dimension, the school culture dimension, the shared responsibility dimension, and the teacher training and professional development dimension. The adoption of these dimensions may be due to her awareness of their importance and direct role in improving the quality of the teaching and learning process and developing its outcomes.

Distributed Leadership is a style of leadership in which leadership authorities and responsibilities are distributed among the institution's members instead of being left to one person who makes decisions and provides guidance. This approach represents a shift from the traditional leadership model that focuses on the leader alone and aims to enhance the sense of responsibility and participation in decision-making among all members of the institution (Hulpia et al., 2012). Distributed leadership has several characteristics, including: Distributed leadership shows remarkable success in dealing with challenges, threats, and rapid changes, strongly encourages the exchange and sharing of good ideas, and develops and transforms them into tangible realities. This makes it rely on teamwork to achieve positive results (Al-Masara, 2019). Distributed leadership focuses on integrating the team's experiences with the leader's expertise to improve and develop school leadership. It encourages the adoption of new and non-traditional methods to keep pace with educational developments and the accompanying challenges. By adopting distributed leadership, innovative methods for dealing with events and potential risks can be accessed (Kempster et al., 2013). In a work environment characterized by distributed leadership, mistakes become opportunities to discover new valuable approaches and directions (Harris, 2011). The distributed leadership approach gives each individual the ability to make their job more effective, efficient, and significant. Distributed leadership emphasizes that each individual has their value, impact, and importance in achieving common goals (Woods & Roberts, 2016). Additionally,

distributed leadership enhances cooperation and trust among team members instead of competition, where consensus is achieved among everyone regarding the school's vision despite the varying contributions of individuals. This contributes to enhancing belonging and loyalty to the school (Akdemir & Ayik, 2017).

The success or failure of school principals' application of distributed leadership in schools is influenced by a set of factors summarized by Harris and Spillane (2008) as follows:

Community Culture: Distributed leadership carries a shift in community culture, moving from the traditional leadership model of "single-person leadership" to flexible and effective leadership. The main challenge facing this leadership approach is the presence of a supportive community culture that encourages interaction among individuals and groups, enhancing the success of applying distributed leadership in the school.

Organizational Structures: The organizational structures of the school affect the quality of school leadership and administration. Schools that operate according to traditional models hinder the distribution of leadership and positive interaction between the principal and teachers. In contrast, flexible organizational structures in schools encourage responsiveness to modern developments in school leadership and enhance constructive communication and interaction between the principal and teachers, encouraging the exchange of ideas and experiences, thus helping to improve educational performance and build a stimulating educational environment.

Social Relationships: The various forms of relationships between school administration and teachers, among teachers themselves, and between teachers, students, and their parents influence different directions, including: Trust and positive interaction: When strong relationships based on trust are built between faculty members and administration, it becomes easier for teachers to participate in the decision-making process and contribute to improving school performance. Effective communication: Open relationships and effective communication between leaders and teachers facilitate the smooth exchange of ideas and information, stimulating creativity and innovation, which facilitates coordination and the achievement of educational and learning goals. Building positive relationships also encourages the participation of school team members in making decisions related to curricula, planning, and professional development, giving them a sense of belonging and contribution to the school's success. Moreover, positive and effective relationships contribute to reducing internal conflicts and tensions among faculty members, positively affecting the educational environment and serving to improve the school's overall performance.

By using distributed leadership, the school leader transforms leadership from a top-down hierarchical style to a collective horizontal style, where authorities are distributed, and the energies and expertise of all school staff are gathered under continuous monitoring, mutual trust, participation, and cooperation. This approach leads to increased effectiveness and motivation of the team and improves school performance and the quality of educational outcomes. Thus, the school achieves a competitive advantage and elevates the level of services it provides to its students, making it outperform other schools (Akdemir & Ayik, 2017).

Harris (2011) indicates that distributed leadership provides a sense of security and belonging to school staff, as they are always informed of the latest developments and actively participate in planning and proposing new ideas, which contributes to developing new and diverse skills and methods for them. Distributed leadership is characterized by moving away from traditional bureaucracy and enhancing cooperativeness, as following this model in schools contributes to the positive development of teachers' professional skills and abilities, positively affecting the educational process and student learning.

School leaders in the Arab community within the Green Line face increasing challenges and pressures with the rising expectations placed on schools in an era characterized by rapid and continuous development and change in the educational and technical fields. Therefore, school leaders in the Arab community seek to change their leadership styles and strategies to direct the learning and teaching process toward empowering students and equipping them with the knowledge and skills that help them interact positively in a rapidly changing society. It is worth noting that there are multiple leadership styles practiced in various institutions, such as transformational leadership, transactional leadership, and servant leadership. Distributed leadership has occupied a prominent position in terms of its impact and effectiveness in the interaction among members of the administrative institution. The concept of distributed leadership relies on distributing tasks among staff in a way that achieves fairness and equality. In schools, the need for distributed leadership may be more prevalent, as school community members form an integrated team working together, making this type of leadership necessary. Hence, the idea of this study emerged.

Statement of the Problem and Questions

Through her work in the local council, direct communication with her colleagues in the educational field, and her field visits to schools, which included meetings and encounters with principals and teachers, the researcher noticed that many schools in the Arab community within the Green Line still rely on the principal and the school deputy to manage school affairs. The prevailing leadership style in schools is the traditional style based on the principle of centralization and the concentration of authority in the hands of leaders, with weak involvement of staff and teachers and consultation with them in making decisions related to school issues. This restricts their creativity and prevents the exploration of innovative solutions to these issues. Due to this approach, school performance may be negatively affected, and its ability to improve the student learning process and achieve its goals may diminish.

The study by Al-Aliani and Al-Alfi (2018) emphasized in its recommendations the importance of training school leaders on administrative and leadership skills related to distributed leadership due to its positive reflections on the teacher's psychology and performance. It is based on the principle of mutual trust between principals and teachers, and teamwork is its foundation. Therefore, a skilled leader in organizing it ensures the availability of a flexible and cooperative educational environment that easily adapts to rapid changes and encourages effective participation among all school community members, enhancing school administration performance and thus the school's success in achieving its goals. From this perspective, the researcher's idea for the study emerged in an attempt to answer the following two questions:

- 1. What is the degree of practicing distributed leadership by Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line from the teachers' perspective?**
- 2. Do the estimates of Arab school teachers in the Northern District within the Green Line regarding the degree of their principals' practice of distributed leadership differ according to the variables (gender, educational qualification, and years of service)?**

Study Objectives:

The study sought to achieve the following objectives:

To identify the degree of practicing distributed leadership by Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line from the teachers' perspective, to work on improving this degree by providing appropriate training programs for school principals in the field of distributed leadership.

To reveal the differences in the estimates of Arab school teachers within the Green Line regarding the degree of their principals' practice of distributed leadership according to the variables (gender, educational qualification, and years of service), to provide appropriate recommendations to decision-makers regarding these differences.

Significance of the Study

The importance of the study is as follows:

Theoretical Importance

It is hoped that this study will enrich the theoretical aspect and the Arab library by providing data, information, and knowledge about the concept of distributed leadership. This is achieved by presenting an appropriate theoretical framework for the study's topic. It may be one of the few Arab studies that have explored distributed leadership among school principals in the Arab community within the Green Line, thus enriching the theoretical literature in this field.

Practical Importance

Directing the attention of decision-makers in the Ministry of Education to take the results of this study into account to improve practices related to distributed leadership by school principals, through strategic planning to develop training programs for school principals that activate the foundations of distributed leadership, positively reflecting on their performance, and consequently on the performance of teachers in particular and the school in general.

The results of the current study may benefit school leaders in improving their degree of practicing distributed leadership, which may positively reflect on the educational process in their schools, and thus the school's success in achieving its goals.

The results of the current study may benefit researchers and postgraduate students, guiding them to conduct similar studies on the topic of the current study, in light of the results concluded by this study.

Operational Definitions of Terms

- The study included the following terminological and operational definitions:

Distributed Leadership

It is "an operational approach based on granting the school principal a number of formal and informal leadership roles to teachers and administrators, through delegating authority and participating in decision-making and implementation, practicing school activities, and activating community partnership, aiming to develop school performance" (Al-Yaqoubi, Al-Ani, and Al-Ghanbousi, 2015, p. 82).

Operationally defined: It is a style of leadership that focuses on distributing authority among school community members instead of being concentrated in one person, the principal. This style is characterized by encouraging staff to participate in making and implementing school decisions. It was measured in the current study by the total score obtained by respondents on the distributed leadership questionnaire prepared by the researcher for this purpose.

Study Limitations: The study limitations are as follows:

- **Subject Limitation:** It is represented in revealing the degree of practicing distributed leadership by Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line.
- **Human Limitation:** The study was limited to a sample of male and female teachers working in Arab schools in the Northern District within the Green Line.
- **Spatial Limitation:** The current study was applied in Arab schools in the Northern District within the Green Line.
- **Temporal Limitation:** The current study was applied during the first semester of the academic year 2023/2024.
- **Study Determinants:** The generalization of the results of this study depends on the validity and reliability of the study tool, and on the seriousness and objectivity of the responses of the study sample members to it.

Empirical Studies

In this section, the studies that the researcher was able to access were reviewed, arranged according to the time they were conducted, as follows:

Al-Sharifi and Abdullah (2017) conducted a study aimed at identifying the level of practicing distributed leadership by private secondary school principals in Amman Governorate from the teachers' perspective and revealing the differences in that level according to the variables of gender, educational qualification, and years of experience. The descriptive survey method was used, and a questionnaire was used to collect data. It was applied to a stratified random sample of 341 male and female teachers. The results showed that the level of practicing distributed leadership by private secondary school principals in Amman Governorate was moderate, and there were statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the level of practicing distributed leadership by private secondary school principals in Amman Governorate attributed to the gender variable in favor of females, and no differences attributed to the variables of educational qualification and experience.

Al-Aliani and Al-Alfi (2018) conducted a study aimed at determining the degree of practicing distributed leadership in public education schools in Al-Baha region. The descriptive survey method was used, and a questionnaire was used to collect data and information. It was applied to a sample of leaders and teachers of public education schools in the three educational stages (boys) in Al-Baha Governorate, totaling 486 teachers and 80 school leaders. The results showed that the degree of practicing distributed leadership by school principals was high, and the results did not show statistically significant differences at the significance level (0.05) between the mean responses of the study sample members in their estimation of the degree of practicing distributed leadership by principals attributed to the job title variable.

Al-Masara (2019) aimed to reveal the degree of practicing distributed leadership by public school principals in Al-Mazar Al-Shamali district from the teachers' perspective and to know the impact of variables (gender, years of experience, and qualification) on that degree. The study sample consisted of 317 male and female teachers, selected through stratified random sampling. The descriptive survey method was used, and a questionnaire was used to collect study data. The results showed that the degree of practicing distributed leadership by public school principals in

Al-Mazar Al-Shamali district was high, and there were no statistically significant differences in teachers' estimates of the degree of their principals' practice of distributed leadership attributed to the study variables.

Emilia (2019) sought to identify the degree of practicing distributed leadership by public secondary school principals in Amman Governorate. The study sample consisted of 347 male and female teachers, selected through stratified random sampling. The descriptive survey method was used, and a questionnaire was used to collect data after ensuring its validity and reliability. The results showed that the degree of practicing distributed leadership by public secondary school principals in Amman Governorate from the teachers' perspective was low.

Sharaiha and Al-Sarayrah (2021) aimed to identify the degree of practicing distributed leadership by private school principals in Amman Governorate from the teachers' perspective. The descriptive method was used, and a questionnaire was used as a tool to collect data, distributed to a stratified random sample of 380 male and female teachers from private schools in Amman. The results indicated that the degree of practicing distributed leadership by private school principals in Amman Governorate was high.

Alshehri (2022) aimed to identify the degree of practicing distributed leadership by public school principals in the Eastern Region from the teachers' perspective. The study sample consisted of 361 male and female teachers selected randomly. The descriptive survey method was used, and a questionnaire was used to collect data. The results indicated that the degree of practicing distributed leadership by school principals was high.

Concluding remarks

By reviewing the previous studies that were presented and analyzed, it was noted that they focused on the practice of distributed leadership by school principals. The geographical locations where the previous studies were applied varied, but the researcher, within the limits of her knowledge and research, was unable to find a study that investigated distributed leadership in the Northern District within the Green Line. This is one of the most prominent elements that distinguish the current study from those studies. The previous studies formed the primary source of much important information that guided the researcher in her current study in terms of identifying the problem, formulating it, its methodology, its community, its variables, and the appropriate procedures to achieve its objectives. Additionally, those studies guided the researcher toward many appropriate references, research, and studies, and enabled her to form a comprehensive view of the theoretical frameworks that should be included in the current study. The researcher will benefit from them in discussing and interpreting the results and showing the points of agreement and disagreement between them.

Method and Procedures:

- In this section, the researcher addressed the following:

Study Methodology

The descriptive method was adopted for its suitability to the purposes of this study.

Study Community

- The study population consisted of all male and female teachers working in the Directorate of Education in the Northern District within the Green Line, totaling 22,607

male and female teachers, according to the statistics of the Ministry of Education for the academic year 2023/2024.

- **Study Sample**
- A simple random sample was selected from the study population, totaling 386 male and female teachers, according to statistical tables, in a way that ensures the sample's representation of the population from which it was taken. Table (1) shows this.
- **Table (1): Distribution of Study Sample Members According to Their Variables**

Table 1: Distribution of Study Sample Members by Gender, Years of Experience, and Educational Qualification

Variable	Category	Frequency (n)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	167	43.30
	Female	219	56.70
	Total	386	100.00
Years of Experience	Less than 10 years	134	34.70
	More than 10 years	252	65.30
	Total	386	100.00
Educational Qualification	Bachelor's Degree	94	24.40
	Postgraduate studies	292	75.60
	Total	386	100.00

- **Study Instruments**

To collect the necessary data to achieve the study's objectives, the researcher developed a questionnaire consisting of two parts. The first part included the respondent's personal data, while the second part measured the degree of practicing distributed leadership by Arab school principals within the Green Line from the teachers' perspective. To formulate the items of the (Distributed Leadership) scale, the researcher referred to the theoretical literature and previous studies related to the topic, such as the studies of Sa'ima (2017); Al-Masara (2019); Emilia (2019); and Alshehri (2022). This led to the formulation of 34 items, evenly distributed with 8 items across four domains: the school's vision and mission, school culture, shared responsibility, and teacher training and professional development.

- **Content Validity of the Instrument**
- To verify the content validity of the tool, it was presented in its initial form to a group of experts and specialists in the fields of educational administration, foundations of

education, higher education administration, curricula and teaching methods, and measurement and evaluation at Yarmouk University, Middle East University, Jerash University, and Irbid National University, totaling 10 arbitrators. The purpose was to obtain their opinions on the items in terms of their belonging to the domain, clarity of linguistic formulation, and their appropriateness to the domain they belong to, as well as any modifications and observations they deem appropriate.

- Based on the arbitrators' notes and opinions, the suggested modifications were made, which included modifying the wording of some items. The wording of items (2, 3, 7, 11, 13, 15, 23, 28, 30) was modified, and item (16) from the shared responsibility domain and item (31) from the teacher training and professional development domain were deleted as recommended by the arbitrators. Thus, the number of items in the tool in its final form after rearrangement and renumbering became 32 items.
- To respond to the items of the study tool, a five-point Likert scale was adopted as follows: (Very large and takes 5 points, large and takes 4 points, medium and takes 3 points, small and takes 2 points, very small and takes 1 point).
- **Construct Validity of the Instrument**
- The questionnaire was applied to a pilot sample consisting of 30 male and female teachers from Arab schools in the Northern District within the Green Line, outside the targeted study sample, to calculate Pearson correlation coefficients for the relationship of the items with the domain and the domains they belong to, as shown in Table (2).

Table (2): Pearson correlation coefficients for the items with the domain to which they belong, and with the tool as a whole (n=30)

Total instrument	Domains	Items	No	Domain
0.69	0.63	Provides an ambitious future vision for what the school should be in the future.	1	School Vision and Mission
0.54	0.53	Involves all teachers in developing a vision for the school.	2	
0.32	0.26	Communicates the school's vision and mission to all school staff.	3	
0.47	0.52	Prepares an annual plan to follow up on the achievement of the school's vision and mission in line with the teachers' capabilities.	4	
0.63	0.73	Takes into account the values of society when formulating the school's vision.	5	
0.76	0.74	When formulating the school's vision, he is concerned with its achievability.	6	
0.69	0.77	Coordinates efforts between teachers in line with the school's specific goals.	7	

Total instrument	Domains	Items	No	Domain
0.77	0.82	Holds periodic meetings to follow up on the implementation of work that contributes to achieving the school's vision and mission.	8	School culture
0.73	0.67	Supports teachers' creative ideas.	9	
0.74	0.72	Accepts constructive criticism with an open heart, in a way that serves the general interest of the school.	10	
0.66	0.66	Encourages teachers to exchange experiences with their colleagues inside and outside the school.	11	
0.84	0.79	Promotes a culture of teamwork within the school.	12	
0.69	0.78	Delegates the necessary powers to teachers to perform their tasks to the fullest.	13	
0.75	0.81	Promotes a culture of mutual respect among school staff.	14	
0.79	0.81	Bes keen to be a good role model for teachers.	15	
0.88	0.87	Adopts the principle of consultation in dealing with school issues.	16	
0.47	0.46	Involves teachers in decision-making on school issues.	17	Shared responsibility
0.78	0.80	Provides the necessary support for the teacher to perform his/her leadership role.	18	
0.59	0.57	Gives parents the opportunity to participate in school decision-making.	19	
0.74	0.69	Organizes professional learning communities with the participation of teachers.	20	
0.71	0.70	Involves teachers in addressing student issues at school.	21	
0.53	0.55	Welcomes students to participate in leadership tasks within the school.	22	
0.78	0.78	Allows representatives of school committees to make suggestions on improving the learning process.	23	

Total instrument	Domains	Items	No	Domain
0.78	0.73	Gives teachers the opportunity to perform leadership tasks in communicating with members of the local community.	24	Teacher training and professional development
0.69	0.83	Provides a suitable place for teacher training in the school.	25	
0.72	0.83	Encourages teachers to participate in leadership training programs held inside or outside the school.	26	
0.83	0.91	Ensures that the training programs provided to teachers are consistent with their training needs.	27	
0.80	0.87	Encourages teachers to join graduate programs.	28	
0.62	0.67	Encourages teachers to conduct research projects that contribute to improving school performance.	29	
0.56	0.58	Urges experienced teachers to help new teachers develop their leadership roles.	30	
0.75	0.66	Provides teachers with information sources that help them develop their leadership capabilities.	31	
0.80	0.77	Directs teachers to participate in educational conferences inside and outside the school.	32	

All values are statistically significant at the (0.05) level.

It is noted from the results of Table (2) that the values of Pearson's correlation coefficients for the paragraphs with the domains ranged between (0.26-0.91), and the values of the correlation coefficients for the paragraphs with the tool as a whole ranged between (0.32-0.88), and all the values of the correlation coefficients were statistically significant at the significance level (0.05), and these values are considered acceptable (Al-Kilani and Al-Sharifain, 2011, 431); therefore, no paragraph of the tool was deleted from its two axes.

In addition to the above; Pearson's correlation coefficients were calculated for the relationship of the domains with the tool, and the values of Pearson's inter-correlation coefficients were calculated for the domains with each other, and Table (3) shows that.

Table (3): Pearson's correlation coefficients for the relationship of the domains with the tool, and the values of Pearson's inter-correlation coefficients for the domains with each other

Teacher Training and Professional Development	Shared Responsibility	Shared Responsibility	School Vision and Mission	Statistical	Relationship
			0.91**	Correlation coefficient	School Culture
			0.00		
		0.86**	0.77**	Statistical significance	Shared Responsibility
		0.00	0.00		
	0.85**	0.76**	0.68**	Statistical significance	Teacher Training and Professional Development
	0.00	0.00	0.00		
0.90**	0.94**	0.95**	0.90**	Statistical significance	Total Instrument
0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00		

**Statistically significant at a significance level of (0.01)

It is noted from the results of Table (3) that the values of the correlation coefficients of the domains (the degree of practice of distributed leadership by school principals) with the tool as a whole, and the values of the inter-correlation coefficients of the domains with each other were appropriate, as the values of the correlation with the tool as a whole ranged between (0.90-0.95), while the inter-correlations between the domains ranged between (0.68-0.91). These values are appropriate to achieve the purposes of the current study (Al-Kilani and Al-Sharifain, 2011, 431).

Instrument Stability

For the purposes of verifying the stability of the internal consistency of the tool; Cronbach’s alpha equation was used based on the data of the first application of the survey sample, and for the purposes of verifying the stability stability (Test-Retest) of the tool and its domains; it was reapplied to the survey sample with a time interval of two weeks between the two applications, then Pearson Correlation coefficient was calculated between the values of the two applications, and Table (4) shows the internal consistency stability coefficients and the stability stability of the tool.

Table (4): Cronbach’s alpha coefficients and stability stability of the tool and its domains

Number of paragraphs	Repetition reliability	Internal consistency reliability	Axis and its domains
8	0.92	0.96	School Vision and Mission

8	0.90	0.95	Shared Responsibility
8	0.91	0.95	Shared Responsibility
8	0.93	0.97	Teacher Training and Professional Development
32	0.92	0.94	Total Instrument

It is noted from the results in Table (4) that the values of Cronbach's alpha stability coefficients for the domains of the degree of practice of Arab school principals of distributed leadership ranged between (0.95-0.97), while the values of stability stability for the domains ranged between (0.90-0.93), and the retest stability coefficient for the tool as a whole was (0.92). These values are considered appropriate, and make the tool applicable to the original sample, as indicated by Al-Kilani and Al-Sharifain (2011, 431).

Study instruments correction criterion

The statistical model with relative gradation was adopted; in order to issue judgments on the arithmetic means of the study tool and the domains to which it belongs and the paragraphs that belong to the domains, by dividing the range of numbers (1-5) into five categories to obtain the range of each level, i.e. $(5-1/5=0.80)$, and accordingly the levels will be as follows:

Table (5): Criterion for judging arithmetic means:

Category of Arithmetic Means	Practice Level
5.0-4.20	Very High
-3.40less than4.20	High
-2.60less than3.40	Moderate
-1.80less than2.60	low
-1less than1.80	Very low

Study Variables, Procedures, Statistical Analyses, and Results Presentation

Study Variables

The study included the following variables:

First: Independent Variables, which include:

- **Gender**, with two categories (Male, Female).
- **Educational Qualification**, with two categories (Bachelor's degree, Higher than a Bachelor's degree).
- **Educational Stage**, with two categories (Basic, Secondary).
- **Years of Service**, with two categories (Less than 10 years, 10 years or more).

Second: Dependent Variable

- The degree of practicing distributed leadership by Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line.

Study Procedures

To conduct the study, the researcher followed these steps:

- Reviewing educational literature and previous studies related to the current study topic.
- Determining the study population and sample size.
- Developing the study instrument in its initial form based on a review of educational literature and previous studies.
- Verifying the content and construct validity of the study instrument, as well as its reliability, to finalize the instrument.
- Administering the final version of the study instrument to the target study sample within the specified timeframe.
- Collecting, reviewing, digitizing, and statistically analyzing the questionnaires to answer the study questions.
- Presenting the results, discussing them, and deriving appropriate recommendations based on the study findings.

Statistical Analyses

To answer the study questions, the following statistical analyses were used:

- **To answer the first question:** Means and standard deviations were calculated for the responses of the study sample on the scale measuring the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals within the Green Line.
- **To answer the second question:** A three-way ANOVA was used to identify differences in the responses of the study sample regarding the degree of distributed leadership practice among school principals.

Results Presentation and Discussion

First: Results of the First Question

The first research question was:

"To what extent do Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line practice distributed leadership from the teachers' perspective?"

To answer this question, the means and standard deviations of the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line were calculated from the teachers' perspective. Table (6) presents the results.

Table (6): Means and Standard Deviations of the Degree of Distributed Leadership Practice by Arab School Principals Across Domains (Ranked in Descending Order)

Rank	Domain Number	Domain	Mean	Standard Deviation	Degree of Practice
1	3	Shared Responsibility	4.01	0.95	High
2	1	School Vision and Mission	3.98	0.88	High
3	4	Teacher Training and Professional Development	3.86	0.74	High
4	2	School Culture	3.83	0.93	High
Overall Score	-	Total Degree	3.92	0.78	High

Results Interpretation

The results in Table (6) indicate that the participants rated the overall degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line as **high**, with a mean score of **3.92** and a standard deviation of **0.78**.

The domains were ranked as follows:

- **Shared Responsibility** ranked first, with a mean of **4.01** and a standard deviation of **0.95**, rated as **high**.
- **School Vision and Mission** came in second place, with a mean of **3.98** and a standard deviation of **0.88**, also rated as **high**.
- **Teacher Training and Professional Development** ranked third, with a mean of **3.86** and a standard deviation of **0.74**, rated as **high**.
- **School Culture** ranked last, with a mean of **3.83** and a standard deviation of **0.93**, still rated as **high**.

Discussion of the Findings

These results suggest that teachers in the Northern District within the Green Line perceive their school principals as highly engaged in **shared responsibility**, working diligently to clarify the school's vision, mission, and goals. Principals actively **communicate a clear vision** that reflects the school's aspirations and future priorities while considering community values during the vision development process.

Additionally, they **foster a strong school culture** and **encourage teachers' professional development** by motivating them to participate in **postgraduate programs, educational**

seminars, and both local and international conferences. Principals also **promote leadership roles among teachers by delegating responsibilities and granting them the necessary authority** to perform their duties effectively.

Comparison with Previous Studies

The findings of this study align with the results of **Al-Alyani and Al-Alfi (2018), Al-Masarwa (2019), Shrayha and Al-Saraira (2021), and Alshehri (2022)**, all of which indicated a **high level of distributed leadership practice among school principals.**

However, these findings contradict the study of **Al-Sharifi and Abdullah (2017)**, which reported a **moderate level of distributed leadership practice**, and **Emilia (2019)**, which found that **school principals exhibited a low level of distributed leadership practice.**

For further insights, means and standard deviations were calculated for participants' responses to **each individual item within the "Shared Responsibility" domain**, ranked in descending order based on their overall mean scores, as shown in **Table (7).**

1 Table (7): Arithmetic Means and Standard Deviations for Items in the (Shared Responsibility) Domain, Ordered Descendingly

Order	Item No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Practice Level
1	21	Engages teachers in addressing student issues at school.	4.26	1.11	Very High
2	20	Organizes professional learning communities with teacher participation.	4.17	1.14	High
3	24	Gives teachers the opportunity to take on leadership roles in communicating with local community members.	4.10	1.25	High
4	22	Welcomes student participation in performing leadership tasks within the school.	4.01	1.18	High
5	18	Provides the necessary support for teachers to perform their leadership roles.	3.99	1.21	High
6	19	Allows parents of students to participate in school decision-making.	3.99	1.23	High
7	17	Involves teachers in making decisions related to school issues.	3.80	1.24	High
8	23	Allows representatives of school committees to present proposals for improving the learning process.	3.78	1.23	High

Total for the Shared Responsibility Domain | 4.01 | 0.95 | High

Observations from Table (7):

The results in Table (7) show that the overall arithmetic mean of the sample's ratings for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line for items in the (Shared Responsibility) domain was (4.01), with a standard deviation of (0.95), indicating a high level of practice. This result may be attributed to the fact that teachers perceive their relationship with their principals as complementary. Principals treat all teachers objectively, without bias or discrimination, and involve them in various school committees and decision-making processes related to school issues. This likely stems from the principals' trust in the teachers' capabilities and potential. Additionally, the relationship between principals and teachers is built on mutual trust, respect, and cooperation. As a result, principals motivate teachers, enhance their work engagement, and delegate some of their authority to them to undertake leadership tasks inside and outside the school to achieve the school's administrative and educational goals. This has positively reflected on teachers' ratings of their principals' distributed leadership practices in this domain.

The highest-rated item was (21), which states, "Engages teachers in addressing student issues at school," ranked first with an arithmetic mean of (4.26), a standard deviation of (1.11), and a very high practice level. This may be because teachers are closer to students, spending more time with them in the classroom than the principal. Thus, teachers are more aware of student issues and their circumstances. Therefore, the school principal involves teachers in addressing student issues due to trust in their abilities and because it enhances effective learning and contributes to building a stimulating and suitable learning environment for all students.

Item (20), which states, "Organizes professional learning communities with teacher participation," came in second place with an arithmetic mean of (4.17), a standard deviation of (1.14), and a high practice level. This may be due to the principals' belief in the importance of these professional communities and their role in improving the quality of education. Therefore, they are keen to organize these communities with teacher participation, emphasizing their significance. Additionally, the Ministry of Education's focus on teacher development and skill improvement positively impacts their performance and, consequently, the school's performance, which is reflected in the teachers' high ratings for this item.

Item (23), which states, "Allows representatives of school committees to present proposals for improving the learning process," came in last place with an arithmetic mean of (3.78), a standard deviation of (1.23), and a high practice level. This result may be attributed to the sample's recognition of the leadership role played by these committee representatives and their role in improving school performance. Therefore, school principals ensure that committee representatives have the opportunity to present ideas, proposals, and creative initiatives that contribute to improving and developing the teaching and learning process.

Second: The Domain of School Vision and Mission

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sample's ratings for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line for items in the (School Vision and Mission) domain were calculated, ordered discerningly based on their overall arithmetic means, as shown in Table (8).

Table (8): Arithmetic Means and Standard Deviations for Items in the (School Vision and Mission) Domain, Ordered discerningly

Order	Item No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Practice Level
1	1	Presents an ambitious future vision for what the school should become.	4.30	1.00	Very High
2	7	Coordinates efforts among teachers in line with the school's defined goals.	4.22	1.12	Very High
3	3	Disseminates the school's vision and mission to all school staff.	4.07	1.13	High
4	8	Holds regular meetings to follow up on tasks contributing to achieving the school's vision and mission.	3.94	1.20	High
5	2	Involves all teachers in developing the school's vision.	3.91	1.21	High
6	6	Ensures the school's vision is achievable when formulating it.	3.87	1.18	High
7	4	Prepares an annual plan to follow up on achieving the school's vision and mission in line with teachers' capabilities.	3.80	1.20	High
8	5	Takes community values into account when formulating the school's vision.	3.76	1.29	High

Total for the School Vision and Mission Domain | 3.98 | 0.88 | High

Observations from Table (8):

The results in Table (8) show that the overall arithmetic mean of the sample's ratings for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line for items in the (School Vision and Mission) domain was (3.98), with a standard deviation of (0.88), indicating a high level of practice. This result may be attributed to the fact that the study sample believes that school principals recognize the importance of the role teachers play in the success of school operations. Therefore, they provide opportunities for all teachers to participate in developing the school's vision and mission, ensuring that the vision reflects the school's future ambitions and is achievable given the available resources and in line with teachers' capabilities and skills. Additionally, principals emphasize the values sought by the community surrounding the school when formulating the vision and mission, as they believe in the role community members play in school operations.

The highest-rated item was (1), which states, "Presents an ambitious future vision for what the school should become," ranked first with an arithmetic mean of (4.30), a standard deviation of (1.00), and a very high practice level. This result reflects the great importance of providing an ambitious future vision for the school from the teachers' perspective. Presenting such a vision clarifies the ultimate goal or desired state the school should achieve in the future, helping teachers understand the direction the school is heading and fostering a sense of connection and shared orientation toward achieving this vision. Hence, teachers' ratings were very high.

Item (7), which states, "Coordinates efforts among teachers in line with the school's defined goals," came in second place with an arithmetic mean of (4.22), a standard deviation of (1.12), and a very high practice level. This may be due to the positive and amicable human relationships

between the principal and teachers, which are based on complementary work. The relationship between the principal and teachers is built on consultation, cooperation, and joint work. Therefore, the principal ensures that tasks are distributed and efforts are coordinated among teachers to achieve the school's goals with the highest degree of quality and effectiveness.

Item (5), which states, "Takes community values into account when formulating the school's vision," came in last place with an arithmetic mean of (3.76), a standard deviation of (1.29), and a high practice level. This may be attributed to the fact that incorporating community values into the school's vision enhances social integration and strengthens the sense of belonging to the school as an important educational institution in the community. Respecting and including community values in the school's vision helps build sustainable and strong positive relationships with parents and increases their participation in supporting school activities and initiatives. Therefore, the principal considers community values when formulating the school's vision to ensure the achievement of educational goals and effectively serve the local community's interests.

Third: The Domain of Teacher Training and Professional Development

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sample's ratings for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line for items in the (Teacher Training and Professional Development) domain were calculated, ordered discerningly based on their overall arithmetic means, as shown in Table (9).

Table (9): Arithmetic Means and Standard Deviations for Items in the (Teacher Training and Professional Development) Domain, Ordered discerningly

Order	Item No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Practice Level
1	31	Provides teachers with information resources that help them develop their leadership capabilities.	3.98	1.01	High
2	26	Encourages teachers to participate in leadership training programs held inside or outside the school.	3.97	1.30	High
3	32	Guides teachers to participate in educational conferences inside and outside the school.	3.96	0.96	High
4	30	Urges experienced teachers to help new teachers develop their leadership roles.	3.91	1.08	High
4	25	Prepares a suitable space for teacher training within the school.	3.91	1.30	High
6	27	Ensures that the training programs provided to teachers align with their training needs.	3.81	1.27	High
7	29	Encourages teachers to undertake research projects that contribute to improving school performance.	3.70	1.05	High
8	28	Encourages teachers to enroll in postgraduate programs.	3.66	1.10	High

Total for the Teacher Training and Professional Development Domain | 3.86 | 0.74 | High

Observations from Table (9):

The results in Table (9) show that the overall arithmetic mean of the sample's ratings for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line for items in the (Teacher Training and Professional Development) domain was (3.86), with a standard deviation of (0.74), indicating a high level of practice. This result can be attributed to the fact that teachers recognize the significant role played by the Ministry in the professional development of principals, which has reflected on their practices toward teachers. Principals understand the role of teachers in the success of the teaching and learning process and in improving its outcomes. Therefore, they encourage teachers to participate in training programs and workshops organized by the Ministry, as these have a positive impact on teacher performance and productivity. They also motivate teachers to enroll in postgraduate programs by reducing their workload and to undertake research projects that contribute to school development and improvement. This has positively influenced teachers' responses, resulting in high ratings for this domain.

The highest-rated item was (31), which states, "Provides teachers with information resources that help them develop their leadership capabilities," ranked first with an arithmetic mean of (3.98), a standard deviation of (1.01), and a high practice level. This may be because the sample recognizes the importance of the role school principals play in achieving the school's vision, which stems from the Ministry of Education's vision focusing on developing teachers' skills and leadership capabilities. Therefore, principals ensure the provision of all necessary equipment and information resources to teachers to improve their educational performance, support their professional development, and enhance their leadership capabilities in a way that ensures the effective achievement of school goals. Providing such resources builds a strong bridge of communication between the principal and teachers, fostering mutual understanding.

Item (26), which states, "Encourages teachers to participate in leadership training programs held inside or outside the school," came in second place with an arithmetic mean of (3.97), a standard deviation of (1.30), and a high practice level. This may be due to the significant efforts made by the Ministry of Education in the professional growth of school principals and teachers through organizing training programs and workshops in educational leadership, as well as field visits. Additionally, the role of the Educational Supervision Department in organizing necessary workshops and training programs for teachers to develop their leadership capabilities has contributed to the teachers' high ratings for this item.

Item (28), which states, "Encourages teachers to enroll in postgraduate programs," came in last place with an arithmetic mean of (3.66), a standard deviation of (1.10), and a high practice level. This can be attributed to the principals' belief in the importance of the teacher's role in teaching. Therefore, they encourage teachers to enroll in postgraduate programs, as these programs positively impact teaching performance by improving teaching methods and providing opportunities for specialization. This enhances teachers' expertise, opens doors for career advancement, and improves their living conditions, leading to high ratings from teachers for this item.

Fourth: The Domain of School Culture

The arithmetic means and standard deviations of the sample's ratings for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the

Green Line for items in the (Shared Responsibility) domain were calculated, ordered discerningly based on their overall arithmetic means, as shown in Table (10).

Table (10): Arithmetic Means and Standard Deviations for Items in the (Shared Responsibility) Domain, Ordered discerningly

Order	Item No.	Item	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation	Practice Level
1	14	Promotes a culture of mutual respect among school staff.	4.13	1.12	High
2	9	Supports teachers' creative ideas.	3.98	1.17	High
3	15	Strives to be a good role model for teachers.	3.88	1.27	High
4	13	Delegates necessary authority to teachers to perform their tasks effectively.	3.86	1.17	High
5	10	Accepts constructive criticism openly and in a way that serves the school's best interests.	3.81	1.28	High
6	11	Encourages teachers to exchange experiences with colleagues inside and outside the school.	3.81	1.29	High
7	16	Adopts the principle of consultation in dealing with school-related issues.	3.65	1.27	High
8	12	Promotes a culture of teamwork within the school.	3.53	1.36	High

Total for the School Culture Domain | 3.83 | 0.93 | High

Observations from Table (10):

The results in Table (10) show that the overall arithmetic mean of the sample's ratings for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line for items in the (School Culture) domain was (3.83), with a standard deviation of (0.93), indicating a high level of practice. This result can be attributed to the fact that school principals have moved away from traditional leadership styles based on dominance and have adopted democratic practices, promoting values of participation and cooperation. This is achieved by fostering a culture of mutual respect, teamwork, empowering teachers, delegating necessary authority, and involving them in decision-making processes.

The highest-rated item was (14), which states, "Promotes a culture of mutual respect among school staff," ranked first with an arithmetic mean of (4.13), a standard deviation of (1.12), and a high practice level. This result may be because the sample observes this in practice through the principals' interactions with them and their emphasis on gaining their trust, recognizing the importance of mutual trust and respect in achieving the school's goals. Mutual respect contributes to creating a positive and motivating work environment where everyone feels comfortable and

valued. When mutual respect exists, communication between teachers and the principal becomes more effective, enhancing the team's ability to work harmoniously and collaboratively to achieve school goals.

Item (9), which states, "Supports teachers' creative ideas," came in second place with an arithmetic mean of (3.98), a standard deviation of (1.17), and a high practice level. This may be because teachers perceive that their principals recognize the importance of encouraging creativity in the school environment and its role in improving school performance. Principals actively support creative initiatives and ideas proposed by teachers, reflecting their full appreciation of teachers' creative abilities and talents, which has positively influenced teachers' responses.

Item (12), which states, "Promotes a culture of teamwork within the school," came in last place with an arithmetic mean of (3.53), a standard deviation of (1.36), and a high practice level. This result may be attributed to the sample's recognition of the principal's belief in the importance of cooperation and teamwork, which enhances positive human relationships among teachers and facilitates the exchange of skills, ideas, and experiences. This, in turn, contributes to creating a comfortable and inspiring learning environment

Second: Results of the Second Question, Which States:

"Do the perceptions of Arab school teachers in the Northern District within the Green Line regarding the degree of their principals' practice of distributed leadership differ based on the variables of (gender, academic qualification, and years of service)?"

To answer this question, the arithmetic means and standard deviations of the degree of distributed leadership practice among middle school teachers in the Northern District within the Green Line were calculated according to the variables of (gender, academic qualification, teaching experience, job title, and specialization), as shown in Table (11).

Table (11): Arithmetic Means and Standard Deviations of the Degree of Distributed Leadership Practice Among Arab School Principals According to Variables

Variable	Levels/Categories	Arithmetic Mean	Standard Deviation
Gender	Male	3.95	0.77
	Female	3.90	0.78
Academic Qualification	Bachelor's Degree	4.01	0.68
	Postgraduate	3.89	0.80
Years of Service	Less than 10 years	3.99	0.72
	10 years or more	3.89	0.80

Observations from Table (11):

The results in Table (11) show apparent differences in the arithmetic means of the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line based on the variables, resulting from differences in the levels and categories of the study variables. To verify the significance of these apparent differences, a three-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted for the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals according to the variables of (gender, academic qualification, and years of service), as shown in Table (12).

Table (12): Results of the Three-Way ANOVA for Sample Members' Perceptions of the Degree of Distributed Leadership Practice Among Arab School Principals According to Study Variables

Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Square	F-value	Statistical Significance
Gender	0.183	1	0.183	0.305	0.58
Academic Qualification	0.729	1	0.729	1.213	0.27
Years of Service	0.945	1	0.945	1.574	0.21
Error	229.459	382	0.601		
Total	231.316	385			

Observations from Table (12):

The results in Table (12) indicate no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the arithmetic means of the sample members' perceptions of the degree of distributed leadership practice among Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line attributed to the gender variable. This result suggests that teachers, regardless of their gender, perceive that the systems, regulations, and instructions governing school operations are the same, whether the school is for males or females. The tasks and responsibilities assigned to male principals are the same as those assigned to female principals, which is reflected in the sample members' responses, showing similar ratings.

This finding aligns with the results of the study by Al-Masarwa (2019), which showed no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the degree of distributed leadership practice among school principals attributed to the gender variable.

However, it contradicts the findings of Al-Sharifi and Abdullah (2017), which indicated statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the degree of distributed leadership practice among school principals attributed to the gender variable, favoring females.

The results also show no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses regarding the degree of distributed leadership practice attributed to the academic qualification variable. This result suggests that teachers' academic qualifications do not affect their perceptions of the degree of distributed leadership practice among school principals. Distributed leadership relies on mutual influence and interaction among the parties involved in the educational process, and teachers perform multiple leadership roles according to their assigned tasks and responsibilities, regardless of their academic qualifications. This is reflected in their responses, which were similar.

This finding aligns with the results of Al-Sharifi and Abdullah (2017), which showed no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the degree of distributed leadership practice among school principals attributed to the academic qualification variable.

Similarly, the results show no statistically significant differences at the significance level ($\alpha = 0.05$) between the arithmetic means of the sample members' responses regarding the degree of distributed leadership practice attributed to the years of service variable. This can be attributed to the fact that teachers observe their principals practicing this leadership approach by involving them in shaping the school's vision, mission, and goals, empowering them administratively, and delegating some leadership responsibilities by involving them in various school committees. This

leaves no room for differences in their perceptions of their principals' distributed leadership practice across its various dimensions.

This finding aligns with the results of Al-Sharifi and Abdullah (2017), which showed no statistically significant differences at the level ($\alpha \leq 0.05$) in the degree of distributed leadership practice among school principals attributed to the years of service variable.

Recommendations:

In light of the findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. **Encourage school principals to continue practicing distributed leadership** in its various dimensions due to its positive effects on the learning process and achieving the school's desired goals.
2. **Organize training workshops for Arab school principals in the Northern District within the Green Line** on the concept, importance, and methods of applying distributed leadership in educational administration to maintain the high level of distributed leadership practice and emphasize the importance of training in this field.
3. **Conduct further studies on the same topic** from different perspectives not covered in the current study, linking the concept of distributed leadership to other organizational and administrative variables, and exploring it in different communities and demographic contexts, such as educational stages and school types.

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